

Fluctuation quench and hydrophobic collapse of polymers and biopolymers in water-DMSO binary mixture at low DMSO concentration[†]

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Abstract : Binary mixtures have strong influence on activities of polymers and biopolymers even at low cosolvent concentration. Among the several aqueous binary mixtures studied, water-DMSO especially stands out for its unusual behavior at certain specific concentrations of DMSO. In the present work, we study the effect of water-DMSO binary mixture on polymers and biopolymers by taking a simple linear hydrocarbon chain of intermediate length ($n = 30$) and the protein lysozyme, respectively. We find that at a mole fraction of 0.05 of DMSO ($x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$) in aqueous solution, the hydrocarbon chain adopts the collapsed conformation as the most stable and rigid state. In this case of 0.05 mole fraction of DMSO in bulk, the DMSO concentration in the first hydration layer around the polymer is found to be as large as 17%. Formation of such hydrophobic environment around the polymer is the reason for the collapsed state gaining so much stability. Interestingly, similar quench of conformational fluctuation is also observed for the protein investigated. It is observed that in the case of alkane polymer chains, long wavelength fluctuation gets easily quenched, the polymer being purely hydrophobic. However, in case of the protein, quench of fluctuation is prominent only at the hydrophobic surface, and quench of long wavelength fluctuation becomes insignificant for the full protein. As protein contains both hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties, the extent of quench of conformational fluctuation with respect to that in pure water is almost half for the biopolymer complex (16.83%) than the same for pure hydrophobic polymer chain (32.43%).

Keywords : Polymer conformation fluctuation, water-DMSO binary mixture, radius of gyration, enhanced enzymatic activity.

I. Introduction

Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) is a unique solvent among polar fluids. DMSO and its mixture with other cosolvents, especially water, have attracted substantial attention among scientists in the last few decades. From the studies on some physicochemical properties of DMSO^{1,2} it is found that in neat solvent it remains in a highly associated form through interaction between the non bonding electrons of sulphur and oxygen³, which are liable to rupture by the effect of temperature or in the presence of any proton donor solvents like water.

Among commonly used aqueous binary mixtures, water-DMSO mixture exhibits some exclusive characteristics which include its special and somewhat surprising solvating ability of biopolymers at low DMSO concentrations, as well as behaving as a denaturant at higher DMSO concentrations. Due to its associative nature, water-DMSO binary mixture displays a strong anomalous, non-ideal

behavior at certain specific concentrations of DMSO that is revealed in a number of physical properties⁴. Importantly, it increases enzymatic activity at low DMSO concentration, but decreases the same at higher DMSO concentration. It also acts as a protein stabilizer at low DMSO concentration^{5,6} whereas as a protein destabilizer at higher DMSO concentration⁷.

Although there have been a number of studies to understand the nature and origin of anomalous behavior of water-DMSO binary mixture, no such systematic study has been done till date to understand the reason behind the enhanced enzymatic activity or the enhanced stability of the proteins in lower range of concentration of DMSO, to the best of our knowledge. To find the same, we have designed a simple model by taking linear hydrocarbon chains of intermediate length ($n \sim 30$) in explicit water-DMSO binary mixture. These linear hydrocarbon chains constitute an important class of compounds because of

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having direct relevance to experimental systems. They can also be used as theoretical models of many complicated phenomena such as protein folding. In addition, their sufficiently simple framework allows detailed study at low computational cost. Previously, sequence dependent complexation between single strand DNA and PAMAM dendrimers was studied through detailed atomistic molecular dynamics simulations accompanied by free energy calculations and inherent structure determination⁸. In a later work, Chakrabarty *et al.*⁹ have shown a chain-length dependent crossover in the structural properties of linear hydrocarbon chain using detailed atomistic simulation in explicit water. Very recently, the effect of water-DMSO binary mixture on linear hydrocarbon chains of intermediate length ($n = 30\text{--}40$) have been studied at low DMSO concentration¹⁰. Here we report results of two somewhat different studies.

(i) We have carried out molecular dynamics simulation study of linear hydrocarbon chains of intermediate lengths ($n \sim 30$) in an explicit model of water-DMSO binary mixture for different concentrations of DMSO. At $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ we find the hydrocarbon chain to have a high preference for the collapsed conformation and it stays in this conformation for the majority of time. However, in pure water ($x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.0$), the hydrocarbon chain exhibits an alternating fluctuation between the extended form and collapsed form. As the concentration of DMSO is increased from $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ to $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.10$ and 0.125 , the fluctuation of the hydrocarbon chain markedly increases and the extended conformation starts gaining stability. At $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$, we observe another anomaly when the collapsed conformation again gains certain stability. We also find that in the solution having $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$, the concentration of DMSO molecules in the first hydration layer (within a shell of width ~ 0.76 nm) at the surface of the linear hydrocarbon chain is $\sim 17\%$ which we propose as the optimum concentration of DMSO to compel the polymer to remain in collapsed conformation.

(ii) We have also performed a similar molecular dynamics study on a more complicated system by taking a protein, egg hen lysozyme, in water-DMSO binary mixture. Protein is a complex macromolecule containing both polar and nonpolar residues, and thus gives a more accurate view towards the actual biological phenomena occurring in the nature. In recent years, according to rotatory dispersion studies and also optical and infrared spectral analyses indications of some structural perturbations are found upon DMSO binding to the active cleft and the protein surface even at low DMSO concentration¹¹⁻¹³.

Balaram and co-workers have observed that addition of low concentrated DMSO ($> 10\%$ V/V) exerts a cooperative transition of the structure to a new, partially folded state¹⁴. Similarly, several experimental evidences have shown that addition of low concentrations of DMSO can enhance enzymatic activity by increasing the conformational flexibility of the protein¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The interplay between these bio-polymeric systems and the cosolvent therefore has an essential role behind such interesting incidents particularly at low DMSO concentration¹⁹.

To understand the effect of cosolvents on bio-polymeric systems, we study the microenvironment comprising of water-DMSO around the protein, lysozyme using molecular dynamics simulation. We find an initial compaction in the protein conformation ($< 5\%$) followed by a partial unfolding around 5-15% DMSO mole fraction. Here we speculate that the interaction between the hydrophobic residues and the methyl groups of DMSO are mainly responsible behind such compact conformation.

In the present work we report some fascinating results that enrich our recent understanding of the effect of cosolvents on biopolymer for the first time at low cosolvent concentrations regime.

II. Simulation details

Simulations have been carried out by taking a single molecule of the hydrocarbon chain and a molecule of hen egg white lysozyme (pdb file of lysozyme is taken from RCSB Protein Data Bank) individually and solvating it in a cubic box containing water-DMSO binary mixtures of different concentrations at 300 K temperature and 1 bar pressure. Lysozyme is a globular protein with 129 amino acids, of which 69 amino acids are hydrophilic and other 60 amino acids are hydrophobic. The SPC/E²⁰ water model has been employed to take into account the individual water-water interaction. Full atomistic details have been preserved except for hydrogen atoms bound to the carbon atoms, which are treated as united atoms in GROMOS96 53a6 force field²¹. All the molecular dynamics simulations have been performed using GROMACS (version 4.0.5)²². The length of the cubic solvent box is about 7 nm. After steepest descent energy minimization, the NVT system was equilibrated for 5 ns. The temperature was kept constant using the Nose-Hoover thermostat. It was followed by a NPT equilibration for 10 ns using the Parinello-Rahman barostat. Finally, production simulations were performed for 20 ns using integrator time-step of 2 fs. All properties were extracted from the trajectory of the final production run. Periodic boundary

conditions were applied and non-bonded force calculations employed a grid system for neighbor searching. Neighbor list generation was performed after every 5 steps. A cut-off radius of 1.3 nm was used both for neighbor list and van der Waal's interaction. To calculate the electrostatic interactions, we used PME with a grid spacing of 0.16 nm and an interpolation order of 4.

III. Results and discussion

III.1. Quench of conformational fluctuations of linear hydrocarbon chain at low DMSO concentration

In Fig. 1, we monitor the radius of gyration (R_g) of the linear hydrocarbon of chain length $n = 30$ in water-

DMSO binary mixture for six different concentrations of DMSO, from the MD trajectories. Here it is seen that the system has a great preferential stability in the collapsed conformation in a solution of $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$. Here it is interesting to note that in pure water, the chain shows almost equal stability for both the extended and the collapsed conformation. As the DMSO concentration is increased gradually above 0.05 ($x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.10$ and 0.125), the extended state becomes progressively more stable except at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$, where the continuous decrease in the stability of the collapsed conformation ceases, i.e., the relative stability of the collapsed form of the hydrocarbon chain is almost same at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.125$ and 0.15 .

Fig. 1. Molecular dynamics trajectory of the radius of gyration (R_g) of C_{30} in (1) pure water, (2) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$, (3) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.10$, (4) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.125$, (5) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$, (6) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.20$ (arranged from top to bottom) solution, respectively

At $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.20$, once more we find a near equilibrium existing between the collapsed and the coiled conformations.

Same observations can also be made from the relative probability distribution plots (Fig. 2). Here also we find that at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$, the probability to stay in the collapsed form markedly increases. After that the height of the first peak (which signifies the collapsed state) shrinks

other words it can be put forward as, there is 'preferential solvation' of the hydrocarbon chain by the DMSO molecules to make the collapsed form win over the extended coiled one.

However, the anomaly at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$ is attributed to a completely different reason. The collapsed state becoming stable at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$ can be interpreted in terms of the percolation like phase transition of water-

Fig. 2. The simulated probability distribution of the radius of gyration of C_{30} for different concentrations of DMSO. The graphs show the comparative probabilities of the molecule to remain in the collapsed and extended state for different concentration of DMSO.

as the concentration of DMSO is increased except in case of $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$, where it again shows anomalous behavior.

To characterize the reason behind these anomalous behaviors, we have calculated the concentration of DMSO molecules within 0.76 nm cut-off (this value has been taken from the first minimum in the radial distribution function (rdf) plot of the S atoms of DMSO with respect to C_{30}) around the hydrocarbon chain, shown in Fig. 3. We find that at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$, the concentration of DMSO molecules around the linear hydrocarbon chain within the said cut-off is 17.6%, while at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.03$ the concentration of DMSO around the same is 10.5% where the collapsed conformation has lesser stability. Thus we suggest that 17.6% is the optimum concentration of DMSO needed to create a proper hydrophobic environment around the same to stabilize the collapsed form. In

DMSO binary mixture itself in that particular concentration region ($x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.12 \sim 0.16$), as proposed by Bagchi and coworkers^{23,24}. They have found out that in this concentration range, DMSO molecules form some clusters by their methyl groups with the water molecules, which is reflected in the anomalous behavior of the water-DMSO mixture at this particular concentration range. As the DMSO molecules participate in the association, they are less available to interact with the hydrocarbon chain and thus the collapsed state gains more stability compared to the extended one.

The hydrophobic collapse of the linear hydrocarbon chain at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ is further strengthened by the plot of radial distribution function (RDF) of the CH_3 groups of DMSO with respect to the linear hydrocarbon of chain length 30 (Fig. 4). Here it is seen that at the height of the peak is maximum. This implies that the methyl groups of

Fig. 3. Percentage of DMSO within 0.76 nm cut-off of the C_{30} polymer as a function of mole fraction of DMSO in the solution

Fig. 4. Radial distribution function of the CH_3 groups of DMSO with respect to the C_{30} polymer, at different concentrations of DMSO $x_{DMSO} = (1) 0.05, (2) 0.10, (3) 0.125, (4) 0.15, (5) 0.20$ respectively (top to bottom)

the DMSO molecules are coming to a close proximity to the linear hydrocarbon chain and creating a proper hydrophobic environment around it to assist in the collapse transition. But at $x_{DMSO} = 0.10$ and 0.125 , they are gradually moving away from the surface of the hydrocarbon chain. This is reflected from the reduced peak height of the rdf.

Thus we speculate that the accumulation of excess methyl groups around the hydrocarbon chain at low DMSO concentration is responsible for the hydrophobic stabilization of the same, especially stabilizing the turns and knots that are created within it, thereby quenching the long wavelength fluctuations.

In order to have a more realistic view towards this

problem, we have done molecular dynamics study on the protein hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL) containing both hydrophobic and hydrophilic residues in water-DMSO binary mixture.

III.2. Effect of DMSO on site specific conformational fluctuation of protein lysozyme

To examine the solvent environment around protein, we have analyzed the snapshots of the molecular dynamics trajectory of lysozyme in water-DMSO binary mixture as shown in Fig. 5. At $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$, the methyl groups of DMSO are oriented towards the protein surface. This suggests that DMSO at low concentration sol-

of the hydrophobic side-chain atoms from the average equilibrium structure are monitored. The crystal structures of proteins are generally more compact than the equilibrium structure of the same in aqueous environment as the former has only crystal water but does not have sufficient hydration layer. So the equilibrium RMS value of any protein in water has a finite value while comparing with its crystal structure. Therefore, it is more relevant to compare the equilibrium average value of the RMS deviation for different simulations rather than the evolution of the same. In Figs. 6(a) and (b) we plot the average C_{α} RMS deviation (RMSD) from the crystal structure and RMSF of hydrophobic side-chain atoms for vari-

Fig. 5. Surface representation of molecular dynamics trajectory of HEWL in water-DMSO mixture, showing only the methyl groups of DMSO at concentrations, (a) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.10$, (b) $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.20$. Note that at in (a) maximum methyl groups are pointing towards the hydrophobic surface to enhance the hydrophobic solvation. The polar surface is colored as green whereas nonpolar surface is highlighted in orange.

vates the hydrophobic residues of the protein by exposing the methyl groups towards the same. We observe that the hydrophobic solvation process continues till $x_{\text{DMSO}} \approx 0.15$. The orientations of methyl groups start to change their direction from $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15$.

In order to analyze the conformational stability of the protein in water-DMSO binary mixture, C_{α} root mean square (RMS) deviation for each simulation from the crystal structure of lysozyme and RMS fluctuation (RMSF)

ous DMSO concentrations. Both the plots show that initially at very low concentration of DMSO ($x_{\text{DMSO}} \leq 0.05$), the equilibrium RMS fluctuation decreases significantly compared to the same in water counterpart. Protein goes to a more compact structure due to the solvation of exposed hydrophobic residues by the methyl groups of DMSO. In the concentration range $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05-0.15$, RMS value increases gradually suggesting the continuous partial expansion of the protein structure.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Solvent effect on (a) C_α RMSD and (b) RMSF of hydrophobic side-chain atoms. The RMS difference (Å) between the average structures from 30 ns simulations of lysozyme in water-DMSO binary mixture at different mole fractions

The initial compaction also becomes evident from the plot of average non-polar solvent accessible surface area (SASA) of lysozyme around the same concentration range of water-DMSO mixture, as shown in Fig. 7. This figure mimics the same scenario as observed for average C_α RMSD and RMSF plots. Average non-polar SASA explores how hydrophobic surface of the protein behaves in various concentrations of the water-DMSO environment. Evaluation of non-polar SASA becomes more convincing than polar SASA based on the supposition of favorable interaction between the non-polar atoms of protein and the methyl groups of DMSO molecules. The number of methyl-hydrophobic surface contacts starts to drop in the

Fig. 7. Non-polar SASA of HEWL at various water-DMSO contents. Decrease in non-polar SASA reflects the signature of attaining compact configuration of the protein structure at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ (marked in blue)

concentration range $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.15-0.20$.

III.3. Comparison of compact configuration between polymer and biopolymer systems

As a protein is a complex system containing both hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties, the tendency to obtain a stable compact conformation due to hydrophobic solvation should be less in comparison with pure hydrophobic polymer chain. Indeed we find that for the simple linear hydrocarbon chain long wavelength fluctuation gets extensively quenched at low DMSO concentration, whereas for lysozyme long wavelength gets quenched locally, i.e., only at the hydrophobic part of the active site, and not for the whole protein. To compare between these two systems we have also plotted the mean square fluctuation of radius of gyration $\langle \delta R_g^2 \rangle$ both for the protein and C₃₀ against the mole fraction of DMSO (Fig. 8). The graph shows the expected drop of $\langle \delta R_g^2 \rangle$ at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ followed by an increase in the same for both cases. As expected we find from these two plots that while the extent of compaction with respect to that in pure water is 16.83% for protein, the same for C₃₀ is 32.63% at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$. Hence we conclude that hydrophobic solvation through the methyl groups of DMSO plays a crucial role in attaining a stable compact configuration for the polymer and biopolymer systems.

Fig. 8. Comparison of mean square fluctuation of radius of gyration $\langle \delta R_g^2 \rangle$ measured for both biopolymer lysozyme (left) and pure hydrophobic polymer chain C₃₀ (right). $\langle \delta R_g^2 \rangle$ versus mole fraction (x_{DMSO}) of DMSO is plotted. The value drops sharply at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$ in both cases.

IV. Conclusion

The solvent system water-DMSO binary mixture serves as a special class in binary mixture family, because of its exceptional ability to solvate hydrophobic residues of biopolymers at low DMSO concentration. Here we have studied the nature of collapse transition of a simple hydrophobic polymer chain and a biopolymer in water-DMSO binary mixture and indeed found that at very low DMSO concentration ($x_{\text{DMSO}} \sim 0.05$), the collapsed conformation of the hydrocarbon parts finds an amazing stability. The reason for this has been attributed to the creation of a proper hydrophobic environment by the CH₃ groups of the DMSO molecules which assist the hydrocarbon moieties to remain in the collapsed form. In other words, it can be said that, DMSO molecules help in the preferential solvation of the hydrophobic surfaces, and thus stabilize the collapsed form to a great extent. For the simple linear polymer chain we have calculated the concentration of DMSO molecules within 0.76 nm cut-off around the hydrocarbon chain and found it to be $\sim 17\%$, even when the mole fraction in the bulk is 0.05. We suggest this to be the most favorable concentration of DMSO around the hydrocarbon chain to facilitate the hydrophobic collapse. The extent of hydrophobic compaction between the two systems is also compared by evaluating the fluctuation of radius of gyration both for biopolymer and hydrophobic polymer systems. The tendency to attain a stable compact conformation is much higher for hydrophobic polymer chain (32.43%) than the biopolymer system (16.83%) at $x_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.05$. This is quite

expected as biopolymer contains both hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts. This work is particularly and potentially important as water-DMSO binary mixture establishes a unique example of stabilizing biopolymers exceptionally at very low DMSO concentration.

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